

Global Human Resource Trends and Envisioning Workforce Strategy for National Development

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Abstract

Human Resources (HR) are the set of people who make up the workforce of an organization, business sector, industry, or economy. Human Resources Management (HRM) in public administration considers the civil service broadly to include all those employed in mostly the entities funded by the government. Human Resources Development (HRD) is the frameworks for helping employees develop their skills, knowledge, and abilities, which in turn improves the effectiveness of organizations. HRD of a country is positively correlated to its national development. The objective of this paper is to present a broader vision of workforce strategy for national development in Myanmar. The vision entails the productive, sustainable and inclusive future of the country and the capacity to develop and use the skills of its workforce for the national development. A push toward global recruitment is replacing the traditional model of employing from within the country or promoting from within the organization. The effects of globalization on HR have also brought attention to the importance of cross-border legal compliance. A global trend affecting HR is the area of benefits and compensation. One of the emerging trends in global HRM is diversity training and cross-cultural professional development. The ASEAN declared on HRD for the changing world of work at 36th ASEAN Summit. The rapid growth of the young adult population in Myanmar will affect the socioeconomic development plan of the country. Investment in skills development, employment and livelihood opportunities is necessary for national development. This paper provides a glimpse on the global HR trends, needs for the human capital development in Myanmar and key points in general to be considered in envisioning the workforce strategy for national development.

Keywords: *Human Resources Development, National Development, Myanmar, Workforce Strategy*

1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Human resources (HR) are the set of people who make up the workforce of an organization, business sector, industry, or economy. Similar terms include manpower, labor, personnel, or associates. It is a division of the governmental or non-governmental organizations, in which HR responsibilities include compensation and benefits, recruitment, firing, and keeping up to date with any laws that may affect the organization and its employees. Human resource management is a coherent and strategic approach to the management of an organization's most valued assets – the people working there who

individually and collectively contribute to the achievement of its objectives. The term “human resource strategy” usually applies to a set of coordinated decisions and actions which formulates and directs HRH (recruitment, positioning, utilizing, developing, and rewarding) in the context of achieving the organization goals. Human Resource Development (HRD) is the frameworks for helping employees develop their skills, knowledge, and abilities, which in turn improves the effectiveness of organizations. It helps organizations develop their workforce through employee training and career development which improves organizational effectiveness and performance.

The term human capital refers to the economic value of a worker's experience and skills. It is characterized by the knowledge and skills of employees that can be considered as the most significant resource, particularly in intellectual organizations. Human capital is perceived to increase productivity and thus profitability. The more investment an organization makes in its employees, the chances of its productivity and success becomes higher. Investments in human capital development are keys to closing the gaps and preparing for the future. When supported by wise policies and effective implementation, investments in human capital build resilience to the disruptive future while narrowing existing social and economic gaps. Key challenges of HRM and HRD include motivating and compensating public employees to reward passion for public service, managing the political roles of civil servants and their political responsiveness, selecting salient identities to achieve representation and diversity, and reforming the civil service. These challenges may impact individual and organizational performance.

2. OBJECTIVE

Aim: to examine recent and relevant review on global human resources trends, Human Resource Development in ASEAN, and workforce strategy development

Objective: to explore a broader vision of workforce strategy for national development in Myanmar

Goal: to describe the productive, sustainable and inclusive future of the country and the capacity to develop and use the skills of its workforce for the national development.

3. METHODS

This paper is a general literature review, with an informative purpose.

4. GLOBAL HUMAN RESOURCE TRENDS

4.1 Global Recruitment

A push toward global recruitment is replacing the traditional model of employing from within the country or promoting from within the organization. It focused on getting the best person in the available position, no matter if that person lives. HR teams adopting this global recruitment trend value the diversity, and seek to bring those people on board even if there's an added cost in terms of applying for visas or relocating families.

4.2 Cross-Border Legal Compliance

The effects of globalization on HR have also brought attention to the importance of cross-border legal compliance. Employing workers in a foreign country will mean that the company has to follow the laws concerning labor and compensation in that location. All of these cross-border legal concerns are important for the organization to grasp, because there may be serious consequences attached to failure to follow the law.

4.3 Benefits and Compensation

Most of the foreign countries, especially in Europe, have many less-stringent rules and grant their employees much more holiday and family leave time. As a result, some globalized organizations are embracing these progressive HR policies on benefits and compensation and have begun offering things like paternity leave, extended vacation time and flexible working hours to all of their employees.

4.3 Training and Professional Development

The diversity training and cross-cultural professional development includes all types of learning opportunities and further education programs that an organization offers to its employees, including sponsoring formal university coursework, opportunities to attend conferences and networking events and on-the-job training seminars. Their purpose is to encourage employees to become more diverse both in their skill set and in their core competencies.

5. ASEAN AND HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) reaffirmed the commitment to the ASEAN Vision 2025 to build a people-oriented, people centered ASEAN Community where our peoples enjoy higher quality of life and the benefits of community building and recalled that one of the key purposes of ASEAN as stipulated in the ASEAN Charter is to develop human resources through closer cooperation in education and lifelong learning, and in science, technology and innovation, for the empowerment of the peoples of ASEAN and for the strengthening of the ASEAN Community. The ASEAN recognized the importance of collective efforts in the region and each Member State and greater involvement of businesses and industry to accelerate efforts in preparing ASEAN's human resources for the future and resolved to undertake the following actions, taking into account the capacities and resources of the respective Member States, to prepare the ASEAN human resources for the changing world of work and national development of the member states.

1. Cultivate lifelong learning culture in societies and raise awareness of youth, workers and employers on the importance of investing in skills development to adapt to the changing world of work, including education and training;
2. Improve the inclusivity of education and employment for all especially with respect to improving access to and quality of skills training and job opportunities for all especially women, people with disabilities, elderly, those in rural or remote areas and those employed in small and medium enterprises;
3. Endeavour to have an articulated national policy framework and/or action plan on human resource development, towards improved policy coherence and

given the crosscutting concerns for HRD across the policy areas of education, training, and the labor market, and industrial development;

4. Enhance the responsiveness and cohesiveness of labor, educational, economic policies and institutional frameworks in promoting the following aspects towards better employment opportunities, employability, higher income, job security, quality of jobs and enterprise competitiveness, where relevant and within the framework of each Member State:
 - Innovations and the use of technology in teaching and learning approaches;
 - Educational systems that promote competencies that prepare all for lifelong learning and that promote 21st century skills, including green skills;
 - Competencies, productivity, job flexibility (including mobility) of workers;
 - Business models that incorporate re-skilling, up-skilling and new skills acquisition of workers; and
 - Mutual recognition of skills to support mobility of skilled labor.
5. Promote policies and initiatives for lifelong learning which encompasses key stages of education and training (i.e. basic education, technical and vocational education and training (TVET), higher education) and skills development in organizations that will meet current and future skills needs and allow occupational mobility and career development.
6. Enhance leadership of business, industry and educational institutions on human resources development by fostering closer partnerships between the government and private sector, and providing incentives and recognition to companies investing resources in skills training, internships and apprenticeships
7. Promote the utility of TVET by portraying the decent and employment opportunities, school-to-work transition and career progression of TVET graduates; implementing advocacy campaigns; providing support to women, girls and underprivileged groups to enter non-traditional fields of TVET; and encouraging the harmonization of TVET competency standards and recognition in ASEAN Member States
8. Promote demand-driven competencies and qualifications in TVET as well as in higher education by designing curricula and assessments, engaging qualified teaching personnel with up-to-date research on advanced technology that meets the labor market needs which leads to enhanced cooperation with education and training institutions which are industry based
9. Improve accessibility and quality of labor market information, where appropriate, towards strengthened and coherent labor market information systems, including skills forecasts, to support the capacities of governments, educational institutions, business sector and other stakeholders to promote labor market-oriented education and training
10. Promote infrastructure development to ensure access to crucial infrastructure such as on the internet and information technology, so that the opportunities presented by the Fourth Industrial Revolution may be widely enjoyed

11. Strengthen/establish inter-agency bodies on human resource development across the areas of education, training, industrial development, and labor governance, towards improving policy coherence given the crosscutting nature of human resource development
12. Establish the ASEAN TVET Council (ATC) as a platform for coordination, research and development on innovations and monitoring of regional programs that support the advancement of TVET in the region
13. Explore establishing a central pool of funds with contributions from governments, private sector, international organizations and other partners to support priorities and researches on future skills needs
14. Strengthen cooperation and coordination of relevant ASEAN sectorial bodies, private sector, academia, tripartite partners and other stakeholders to facilitate ASEAN's coordinated and holistic approach on human resources development
15. Strengthen cooperation between ASEAN and ASEAN's external partners, including international organizations, to facilitate the sharing of models, good practices, and experiences in advancing human resources development in a changing world of work.

6. WORKFORCE IN MYANMAR

The workforce force participation rate was 64.9 per cent and the employment-to-population ratio was 64.6 per cent in 2018. Both of these rates are more than 28 percentage points higher for men than for women. The total unemployment rate in 2018 was 0.8 per cent, and the youth unemployment rate was 2.0 per cent, both almost at gender parity. The proportion of youths aged 15-24 years not in education; employment or training was 17.4 per cent in 2017. Employment is heavily reliant on agriculture and on medium-skilled occupations.

The rapid growth of a young adult population in Myanmar will affect the socioeconomic development plan of the country. Investment in skills development, employment and livelihood opportunities is necessary to cater for the growing and the emerging youth bulge to create favorable conditions for a demographic dividend in Myanmar. Despite the promising young workforce, Myanmar is still struggling in providing skilled workers for several key sectors, including manufacturing, construction and tourism. As the country is attracting investments, it needs greater number of certification workers, proving their skills to foreign investors. Businesses end up facing a shortage of skilled workers and need to have a long term plan in solving this problem. It is critically important for Myanmar to transform its economy from works based on natural resources to human resources in order to further develop Myanmar's economy. The workers need to be trained so they are able to compete with other workers from neighboring countries.

6.1 Managing intellectual workers in public sector organizations

Public organizations are considered as intellectual if creating innovative approaches concerning fiscal policy, educational and health system, exploration and development, public purchasing procedures and other. An important aspect of assuring a wholesome effective civil service management, including the development of human resources, is the approach of either

centralization or decentralization of matters of personnel management and development in the public administration. Matters of administration of the civil service, organizing tests for recruiting and promoting, creation of a work pay policy and other functions are the responsibility of centralized structures. It also ensures coordinated actions of organizations, objectivity and precision as well as high professionalism, but it also creates flaws such as bureaucracy, delays, and the inability to adapt to changes in external environment in time.

6.2 Aspects covered in National Development

National development is the capacity of the country to raise the standard of living of its residents, which can be achieved by providing individuals with basic livelihood requirements and supplying them with employment, etc. Human capital is positively correlated to economic growth since investment tends to boost productivity. The process of educating a workforce is a type of investment, but instead of capital investment such as equipment, the investment is in human capital. The role of governments is keys to expanding the skillsets and education levels of a country's population. Workers with more education or better skills tend to have higher earnings, which, in turn, increase economic growth through additional consumer spending. Corporate Sector is important for investment in human capital to boost profits and productivity.

7. SUGGESTIONS

The implementation of the workforce strategy for national development will be largely dependent on the changing context and inputs of the regional/state governments and coordination among ministries in the union level. The Government Workforce Strategy explores possible scenario of the workforce challenges faced by the government and proposes actions for the sector to move towards a more sustainable workforce through retention, attraction and development.

7.1 Workforce planning and development

It is critical to effectively manage workforce demand and supply. This is an essential first step in the development of actions to successfully retain, attract and develop the appropriate workforce.

7.2 Investment in skills and technology to achieve productivity

Investment in skills development to adapt to the changing situation should be increased. It is also necessary to improve the access to and quality of education, skills training and job opportunities for all especially women, people with disabilities, elderly, those in rural and/or remote areas and those employed in small and median enterprises.

7.3 Competencies and qualifications that meet the needs national workforce

The capacities of government ministries, educational institutions, business sector and other stakeholders to conduct skills forecasts to promote market-oriented education and trainings should be assessed regularly and improved.

7.4 Human Resource Development policies and financing

It is important to promote development of innovative mechanisms that promote key human resource to promote national economy that may include entrepreneurs, scientists and technologists, management personnel from both governmental and on-governmental sectors and high skilled workers.

8. CONCLUSION

The ultimate purpose of this paper is to present a strategy to ensure the workforce remains skilled, capable and adaptable for the next decade and beyond for the national development in Myanmar. Each ministry and department is responsible for engaging its own employees and will need to play a part in implementing the strategies and ensuring they modified to fit with the organizational structure, and local circumstances. The methods for monitoring and evaluation are essential to measure the achievement of the implementation.

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